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Motivational Level of Bank Staff in the Cape Coast Metropolis

By

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The study sought to determine the level of motivation of staff of banks in the Cape Coast Metropolis. Using a data obtained through self-questionnaires administered to 81 respondents of seven banks in the Cape Coast Metropolis, the study employed a quantitative methodology and the census sampling technique as well as the descriptive-correlational survey designed to establish the levels and factors of motivation of staff of banks in the Cape Coast Metropolis. Relationships were tested at $p < 0.05$. The results showed that even though the staff members of the banks in the Cape Coast Metropolis have an average level of job satisfaction, there were high levels of motivation, recognition, clarity of role, supervision and perceived competence. It was also discovered that age and experience of the staff have no significant relationship with staff motivation.

Keywords: Motivation, Recognition, Role clarity, Supervision, Job satisfaction, Perceived competence, Banks.

INTRODUCTION

The success of any organisation's performance, first of all, depends on the use of the available resources, with human resources being the most important. Thus, an organisation's ability to have motivated employees will determine the success or failure of that organisation (Storwall as quoted by Bergström and Scarpello 2001). The management of human resources, to a great extent, is therefore connected to employee or staff motivation. This is because, in recent years, staff motivation has become a determining factor in the success of any organisation including the banks. The reason may be attributed to the stiff competition that confronts the organizations (i.e. the banks) to win more customers and to meet their demands.

A study was conducted and published in September 2004 about the Banks and Insurance industries, having the most motivated workers. The study revealed that people working in the Banking industry are the ones feeling best at work and are never tired of their job (Storwall, as quoted by Bergström and Ternehäll 2005). This article is therefore dealing with people working in the bank industry, since they are said to be the most motivated, it would be interesting to see what motivates them, to work more effectively. Banks can be said to be playing important roles in the global economy. Amongst these roles is the promotion of savings and investments for all groups of people, which span from the ordinary labourers and workers to the rich land owners and businessmen. Sparsely speaking, banks invest the funds they mobilize in the industry, agriculture, trade and other business activities. This, they do either directly or as loans to other investors. It is mostly through these banks that foreign trade is undertaken. Whether we export or import, it is through banks that money is transferred from one country to another. Levine (2005) holds the view that, through some of these roles, banks have been empirically proven to have contributed significantly in diverse ways to the growth and development of many economies. As such, if there are no banks, a great portion of a country's capital would remain unused. Also, a weak banking sector will not only undermine the long-term sustainability of an economy, but it can also trigger a financial crisis which can lead to economic crises (Valverde et al. 2002).

The Banking Act, 2007 (Act 673) has enabled the banking sector in Ghana to see a lot of reforms in the past years. The Act has included the award of General Banking License to qualified banks and this has allowed many Foreign Banks to operate in the country. It has also enabled many local private and public banks to open new branches. However, the liberalisation of the banks, among other factors, has created a more competitive environment in the banking industry in terms of market share and technology. Thus, to be ahead of their competitors, banks have to be more sensitive to their customers with respect to the quality of products such as customer care and

pricing they offer. Meanwhile, the banks are focusing on promoting and enhancing new and existing products to improve their visibility

in the market. In the light of this, many banks are making huge investments in technology to upgrade and maintain their infrastructure in order to provide new electronic information-based services and to manage their risk positions and pricing. But it must be noted that whatever framework they may apply would not be fruitful unless it is properly applied by the employees. Hence, it will be appropriate for the banks to have relatively satisfied and motivated workforce with a positive attitude towards their job as well as the organisation.

In the service industries such as the banks, staff who are highly motivated by their organisations provide quality and exceptional customer service (Storwall, as quoted by Bergström and Ternehäll 2005). This is because there seem to be a correlation between good customer service and job satisfaction (Yavas et al., 2006). Thus, the management of most banks have capitalized on diverse incentive packages as very effective tools to beat their major competitors. Most banks, for instance, have sought to motivate their employees through various means including monetary incentives, car loans, mortgages, clothing allowances and health allowances. However, whether these incentive strategies and packages have been effective or not is another issue worth investigating. This is because the levels or degrees of motivation may differ from one organisation to another and that care ought to be taken by management (especially in the banks) when formulating policies and guidelines related to staff motivation.

Motivational/incentive packages come in diverse forms, and they differ from organization to organization and employee-to-employee. Therefore, the strategy one organization may adopt to motivate its staff may be entirely different from that of another organization. More so, packages that may motivate one employee in a given organization may not necessarily motivate another in the same category of work. This is because there are many different factors such as recognition, perceived competence, supervision, role clarity and job satisfaction that can affect the levels of motivation of employees (Okorley & Boohene, 2012). Research has shown that quality customer service delivery is crucial for organisations such as banks to survive and effectively compete in today's dynamic and market-driven economy. Thus it is almost impossible for these institutions to survive without the help of skilled and well-motivated personnel since such human resource is fundamentally important in enhancing the productivity and performance of the organisation (Islam & Ismail, 2008). Curtis and Wright (2001) also opine that motivated employees drive high productivity, customer satisfaction and profits. The development of a motivation process and work environment that would therefore assist in ensuring that employees of banks deliver results in accordance with the expectations of both management and employees have become more crucial than ever.

To make the bank staff give their respective banks that competitive edge, efforts must be directed at staff motivation. These efforts will have to begin with an examination of motivation and various related variables that may account for the success of goal attainment. Such variables are found both in the internal operation of the organisation and outside of the organisation's structure. The literature suggests that some of the variables affecting motivation and subsequently performance are recognition, role clarity, supervision, job satisfaction and perceived competence (Oduro & Kwarteng, 2000). This study therefore attempts to examine the current perceptions of existing levels of motivation and inter-relationships among motivation, recognition, role clarity, supervision, job satisfaction and perceived competence. Furthermore, the study examines whether there is any correlation between age and years of experience of bank staff on the one hand and the level of motivation of the staff on another.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive-correlational survey design was used for the research. This design was considered appropriate for the study because it enabled the researcher to describe the factors that influence motivation of staff of the banks and also establish how these factors correlate with staff motivation. Again, the design enabled the researcher to assess the nature and strength of relationships that exist amongst the variables of the present study.

A census of all staff of banks in the Cape Coast Metropolis was conducted using a questionnaire. The questionnaire which was made up of 92 items consisted of four parts labelled (i.e. A, B, C, and D). The Section A comprised six items eliciting information on the demographic details of the population. The Section B which had five subdivisions (i.e. I – V) sought to gather information on other motivational factors/variables. Whereas Parts I and II dealt with issues concerning levels of staff motivation (i.e. motivation variables) and staff recognition, Parts III and IV gathered data on role clarity and supervision. Part V on the other hand sought for information on job satisfaction. In Section C, the questions elicited information on the perceived competence of the bank staff. Finally, Section D sought for recommendations on the improvement in the staff motivational policy of the banks.

The factors of the study (i.e. motivation, recognition, role clarity, supervision and job satisfaction) were measured with a five-point Likert-type rating scale ranging from 1="strongly disagree" to 5="strongly agree" whilst perceived competence ranged from 1="Very Low" to 5="Very High". Classification of the responses for the study

was done to reflect the various decision levels of responses through the use of mean scores. Therefore, the scale for the interpretation (for mean of the means levels of the factors) is as follows: 0 – 2.5 = low; 2.51 – 3.50 = average; and

3.51 & above = high. 15 members of staff of Pro Credit Savings & Loans Company, Cape Coast Branch, were used to pre-test the questionnaire and the reliability co-efficient for the factors of the study ranged between 0.72 and 0.92. The demographic characteristics of the staff were analysed using frequencies and percentages. The mean was used to determine the levels of motivation, recognition, role clarity, job satisfaction, supervision and perceived competence. To ascertain the relationship between the variables of the study, Pearson Moment Product Correlation statistics was used with an alpha level of .05 for all tests of significance and the results presented in tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study found that majority (78%) of the banking staff in the Cape Coast Metropolis are relatively young with a mean age of 32 years. The ages of the youngest and oldest staffs ranged from 20 and 56 years old respectively. The results again showed that banks in the Cape Coast Metropolis are male dominated (69%). This view confirms Kjellander and Kjellander's (2005) position that women prefer other professions to banking because they value their free time (out of work) more than men. Nearly 75% of the staff were employed over the last five years with majority holding university degree.

The study again revealed that the motivational level of staff in the banks in Cape Coast Metropolis is generally high with a mean level of 3.59 (Table 1). This finding supports the findings of Storwall, as quoted by Bergström and Ternehäll (2005) that people working in the Banking industry are the ones feeling best at work and are never tired of their job. In this study, they attributed this mainly to the high affirmative perception (\bar{X} = more than 3.51) by the staff of what the banks provide them in terms of healthcare, T & T allowances and training, etc.) This result suggests that maintenance or improvement in the areas mentioned would considerably lead to high staff motivation. This could mean that bank staff put premium on their health and therefore do everything possible to ensure they are healthy. This finding explains the assertion by Storwall as quoted by Bergström and Ternehäll (2005) that people working in the banking industry are the ones feeling best at work and are the least likely to be sick from work.

The perception of the staff concerning their recognition was also highly scored (Table 1). *Receiving praise from customers and supervisors* as well as *tangible recognition from my supervisors for services rendered* was of high priority to the staff. They also had the perception that both tangible and verbal (intangible) recognition should be highly considered when motivating them. Thus, the finding suggests that improvement in recognition would logically lead to higher improvement in staff motivation. This finding is consistent with a study on health workers by Khowaja et al. (2005) where recognition, appreciation on good performance and respect from their managers and colleagues were considered as critical factors of staff motivation.

Table 1 – Levels of factors of the study

Factors	n	Mean	Level *
Recognition	81	4.40	High
Role clarity	81	4.44	High
Supervision	81	3.94	High
Job satisfaction	81	3.25	Average
Perceived Competence	81	3.84	High

Source: Field Data, 2010 * \bar{X} = 0–2.5 = low; \bar{X} = 2.51–3.50 = average; \bar{X} = 3.51 & above = high

Responses from the study revealed that the staff of the banks in the metropolis perceive their level of role clarity to be high with a mean of 4.44 (Table 1). Although their role clarity level was high, they indicated that *they had no knowledge of how their performances are adjudged in the bank*. The results suggest that the bank staff know what their roles and responsibilities are and what is expected of them. This finding is consistent with the works of Singh (1993) and de Ruyter et al. (2001) where they emphasise that employees with high role clarity are highly motivated.

Concerning supervision, the study revealed that the staff members of the bank receive high level of supervision (\bar{X} =3.94) in the banks (Table 1). The bank's staff indicated they have good relations with their supervisors. Also, it was indicated that their supervisors are friendly and promote participation. However, the respondents are of the view that they should be provided with information on their profession and there should be

frequent supervisory visits in order to improve their motivational levels. In line with this, Kinkard (1998) included that a dissatisfier (hygiene factor) such as inter-personal relations is an important motivation factor for people.

On the issue of job satisfaction, the results showed that the members of staff have an average satisfaction ($\bar{x} = 3.25$) with their jobs (Table 1). Although the overall job satisfaction was rated as average, the staff members see *their jobs as providing positive satisfying pleasure; their jobs being interesting and providing them with the opportunity to use their skills and abilities* interestingly, *they were tired of jobs*. Their response was established or reflected in the low mean rating of 2.26 scored by the item (see Table 1).

On the whole, the study revealed that bank staff in the Cape Coast Metropolis perceives their competence in banking to be high. The competence such as *provision of banking information to customers; deposit and withdrawal transactions; handling of customer complaints and passing entries to rectify an account* highly motivated the bank staff. However, it was discovered that their competency level in handling e-zwich services of the bank is relatively low. This could be because the e-zwich is a new product in the market introduced only in 2008 by the Bank of Ghana. As such, the bank staff may not be very conversant with its operation. Signals from the corporate world and individuals on challenges facing the system reveal a loss of confidence and trust in it. The situation is disturbing as it has compelled users to abandon the e-zwich smart card which has failed to bring relief and comfort in the trading of goods and services in the country. Also, it could be that, customers are not fully patronising the facility because they are sceptical. This could be as a result of lack of information or education on its usage. Also customers would want to see how well the product will perform on the market before using it and that is quite low.

The Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed for the purpose of determining the relationship between motivation and independent variables and the results were presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Matrix of relationships among the Variables

Factors	Mot	Recog	R/C	Sup	J/S	P/C	Age	Exp
Motivation (Mot)	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Recognition (Recog)	.65*	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Role clarity (R/C)	.33*	.35*	1	-	-	-	-	-
Supervision (Sup)	.49*	.63*	.52*	1	-	-	-	-
Job satisfaction (J/S)	.47*	.41*	.19	.29*	1	-	-	-
Perceived Competence (P/C)	.27*	.44*	.16	.26*	.19	1	-	-
Age	.02	-.10	-.09	-.23*	.04	.08	1	-
Experience (Exp)	.02	-.12	.08	-.14	.02	.03	.86*	1

Source: Field Data, 2010 * $p < 0.05$ (N=81)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed a high level of staff motivation in the banks of the Cape Coast Metropolis. The results also showed that the bank's staff members in the metropolis have high levels in the factors that motivate them. These included recognition, role clarity, supervision and perceived competence. However, the bank staff had an average level of job satisfaction. Also, it was observed from the study that some relationship exists among staff motivation, age and experience, but the relationship was not statistically significant.

The findings of this study for management of the banks have important implications with regards to what would motivate their staff. When the bank's staff members in Cape Coast Metropolis are highly motivated; they would contribute in setting the tone of achieving competitive advantage in the banking sector. The banks must ensure and improve *provision of free medical care, provision and payment of transportation allowances, an opportunity to improve competencies through training as well as attending workshops and seminars* in order to motivate their staff. Employee recognition has become most important in employee motivation because many companies are finding out in today's market that larger pay cheques do not build employee loyalty as they once did. Some of the ways in which management can improve on recognition therefore is by strengthening the tenets of verbal and tangible recognition. Introduction of employee hall of fame at branches levels should be encouraged.

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